

PRAPOUNDRIKADI GHRITA MATRA BASTI IN PARIKARTIKA- A CASE STUDY**Amitabh Singh¹, Dr. Bhoomi Soni², Dr. Jitendra Pandey³**¹Pg Scholar, PG Department of Shalya, Quadra Institute of Ayurveda, Roorkee, Haridwar, India.²Asso. Professor, PG Department of Shalya, Quadra Institute of Ayurveda, Roorkee, Haridwar, India.³Asst. Professor, PG Department of Shalya, Quadra Institute of Ayurveda Roorkee, Haridwar, India.***Corresponding Author: Amitabh Singh**

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ABSTRACT

The Ayurvedic term for fissure in ano is Parikartika. The expression "kartanvat vedena" alludes to cutting and scorching pain. In addition, bleeding is an important indicator of the condition. Parikartika is known as one of the most painful disorders. The rising prevalence of this disease can be attributed to poor eating and bowel habits, as well as unhealthy lifestyle choices. This latest incidence affects all age groups and genders. Fissures in ano are a frequent yet problematic condition. Constipation caused by low fibre diets, junk food, and bakery foods can be difficult to treat due to its recurrence. Ayurveda correlates symptoms with Parikarthika. Treatment options include Deepana and Pachana, Vaatanulomana, Avagaaha, Basti Karma, as well as local applications of Madhura, Sheetha, Snigdha Dravyas, Taila Poorana, Lepa, and Pichu Dharana. Taila poorana (basti) is a simple and effective treatment for parikartika sickness due to its cellular absorption mechanism. This study describes how to effectively manage an acute fissure in ano using matra basti of Praoundrikadi Ghrita.

KEYWORDS: *Parikartika, fissure in ano, Prapoundrikadi Ghrita, Matra Basti.***1. INTRODUCTION**

The Ayurvedic Samhita mentions Parikartika in numerous places. The Charak Samhita describes as Complications of Virechana Vyapad (therapeutic purgation). Susruta Samhita describes it as Basti vhyapad, while Kashyapa Samhita refers to it as Garbhini Vyapad (Disease develops during pregnancy) and many other palaces in texts as symptoms of diseases.

Constipation is a root cause of several colorectal disease.^[1] In Constipation patient passes hard stool which breaks the smooth wall of anal verge or longitudinal Split in lower part of anal canal, These medical conditions leads to *Parikartika* (fissure in ano).^[2]

Fissure-in-ano is the most prevalent and painful condition in anorectal illness. It is typically observed in young people and pregnant women. Injuries to the somatic nerve supply to the anal region generate severe discomfort.

In modern science, therapies include analgesics, antibiotics, laxatives and ointments, as well as anal dilatation, sphincterotomy, and fissurectomy. Fissurein-ano surgeries are expensive and require an extended stay in the hospital. All of these techniques have their own limitations and complications.

Ayurveda offers several medicines as well as the greatest surgical procedures. The ailment fissure-in-ano, which is widespread in ano-rectal practice, shares the same location, pathology, and clinical symptoms as Parikartika, such as anal pain, burning feeling in the anal area, constipation, blood-stained stools, and so on.

In Ayurvedic science, the treatment methods for fissure-in-ano are Sneha basthi (oil enema therapy), Avagaha Swedana (medicated lukewarm water sitz bath), and Lapanam (medicated ointments). Parikartika might be considered as Sadhyo Vrana due to the existence of painful longitudinal ulcer.

Vranaropana-based treatments are more beneficial for treating Parikartika. Prapoundrikadi Ghrita^[3] Matra

Basti^[4,5] offers benefits for pain relief, wound cleansing, and wound healing. Parikarthika can be effectively managed with its qualities.

2. CASE REPORT

In this case study, a 35-year-old male patient presented to Our hospital had a major complaint of Gudashool (cutting pain at the anal fissure), Gudagat Raktasrava (streaking of stool while defecation), burning feeling at anal region, Vibandha (Constipation).

The patient has been experiencing the symptoms listed above for the past 7 days.

3. PERSONAL HISTORY

Rural resident, Mixed Diet, Disturbed sleeping pattern with irregular bowl habits. And Vata-pittaja prakruti.

Investigation done.

Hb -11 gm%

- TLC - 6800
- RBS -114 mg/dl
- HIV –Negative
- HBsAG –Negative
- VDRL -Non reactive

4. HISTORY OF PRESENT ILLNESS

Before 7 days ago, the patient was normal. gradually growing signs such as cutting type.

Pain and burning sensations during defecation and after the faeces, linked with bleeding. rectum and history of constipation in the patient. He came to our hospital for treatment.

A per rectal examination was conducted to analyse the Proper diagnosis. On inspection, a cut longitudinally At 6 O' clock position., an ulcer with indurated margin was detected. There is. There is no exterior pile mass, and no fistula openings and with no Skin tag.

5. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Material used

- Prapoundrikadi Ghrita.
- Sterile gloves- Q.S
- Sterile gauges- Q.S
- Measuring scale
- Disposable syringe- 50ml
- Disposable rubber catheter 10 no.
- Vessels
- Luke warm water

6. CHIKITSA (TREATMENT PROCEDURE)

A case study was undertaken at Quadra Institute of Ayurveda and Hospital, Beld, Roorkee, Haridwar, Uttarakhand.

- Patient was informed about study and consent form will be signed.
- Patients was advised to follow *Pathya, Apathya, Aahar, Vihar* while treatment and in follow-up period too.

- *Prapoundrikadi Ghrita* was manufactured as per standard *Ayurvedic* classical texts, in pharmacy of our Institute, Quadra Institute of Ayurveda, Roorkee, Haridwar.

Poorva Karma

- The patient will be advise to have a light meal on treatment days. Before administration of *Matra Basti, Abhyanga* of *Kati Pradesh* will be done.
- Thereafter, Localized *Nadi Swedana* will be done.^[6]

Pradhan Karma

- Patient is made to lie down on table in left lateral position.^[7] 50 ml of lukewarm *Prapoundrikadi Ghrita* will be loaded in a syringe. A rubber catheter oleated with *Ghrita* will be attached to the enema syringe. Rubber catheter will be introduced through anal orifice, slowly *Ghrita* will be injected.^[18]

Pashchat karma

- After the administration of *Basti*, the patient will be advised to stay in supine pose.^[8]
- After 10 minutes, the patient will be allowed to get up from table and then advised to rest for atleast 30 minutes on bed.

Treatment lasted a total of 14 days.

7. GRADING OF PARAMETERS

Bleeding

- G0-Nill- no bleeding
- G1- Mild- in streaks
- G2- Moderate- drops
- G3- Severe- Profuse bleeding

Pain

- G0- Patients is free from pain
- G1- Bearable pain as stool passes, does not require any treatment)
- G2- Pain during defecation, resolve only after taking analgesics.
- G3- Unbearable and continuous pain, resolve after taking strong analgesics.

Constipation

- G0- No (regular defecation without difficulty)
- G1- Mild (Regular defecation with difficulty)
- G2- Moderate (Irregular hard defecation with difficulty)
- G3- Severe (pellet like defecation ones in a week with difficulty)

Size of split

- G0- Nill
- G1- Small – 0-0.5 cm
- G2- Medium- 0.5-1 cm
- G3- Big- > 1 cm

Skin tag

- G0- Absent
- G1- Present

ASSESSMENT CHART

Subjective & Objective criteria	0 day [B.T]	7 st day	14 th day [A.T]	follow up
Bleeding	2	1	0	0
Pain	2	2	1	0
Constipation	2	2	1	1
Size of split	1	0	0	0
Skin tag	0	0	0	0

7. PROBABLE MODE OF ACTION OF THERAPY
Prapoundrikadi Ghrita ingredients^[9] Prapoundarika, Manjishtha, Madhuka, Ushera, Padmaka, Haridra, Go-Ghrita, Go-Dugdha are having properties like Raktstambhan, Dahaprashaman, Vransodhak and Vranropan Guna, which are usefull in management of Parikartika.

Matra Basti is a specific type of Basti in which small amount of therapeutic oil/ghee/herbal decoction administered through anal route. Moreover, the herbs used in Basti (like Yashtimadhu, Dashamoola, etc.) possess anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and wound-healing properties. These contribute to faster epithelial regeneration and symptom relief. Acordind to contemporary science Basti drugs can be absorbed by rectal mucosa. It works at local as well as systemic level.

8. DISCUSSION

Fissure in ano is a painful anorectal illness characterised by an abrupt superficial rupture. The anal canal remains continuous. Parikarthika is classified as Sadya Vrana due to the presence of a painful longitudinal ulcer. Treatment strategies for fissures in ano should focus on medications that promote ulcer repair and alleviate discomfort. Prapoundrikadi Ghrita medicines used by the patient has unique features, as previously noted. This medication effectively reduces pain, Constipation, and blood seeping during and after defecation.

Due to these properties of Prapoundrikadi Ghrita matra basti 50ml makes it a good treatment option in the management of Parikarthika. Vrana shodhana, vrana ropana, and Rakta Shodhana property of improves the vascular circulation in the anorectal region and reduces spasms and congestion. It has antibacterial, antifungal, anti analgesic properties due to these properties, helps in the healing of anal fissures.

9. CONCLUSION

A case having features of Parikartika (fissure in ano) was selected from OPD, Hospital Quadra Institute of Ayurveda and hospital Roorkee, Haridwar, UK for case study and Praoundrikadi Ghrita matra basti 50ml to patient and patient adviced to take basti for 14 days. Assessment was done based on features like pain, Blood streaking, Constipation and Split size. Significant improvement was observed after treatment, the treatment principle of fissure in ano should be based on the aim to healing of ulcer, reduction of pain and burning sensation and also to correct the constipation. formulation in this

case is satisfy the above mentioned treatment principles. hence we concluded that Prapoundrikadi Ghrita Matra Basti is effective treatment in Parikartika (Fissure-in-ano).

10. DIETARY RECOMMENDATIONS (AAHAR)

Increased fluid consumption. Fibres are foods in the diet. The recommended meal plan includes cow milk and buttermilk, wheat, ghee, rice, fresh vegetables, and a balanced diet. Avoid spicy, fried, and constipation-causing foods.

12. LIFESTYLE CHANGES (VIHAR)

Avoid long sitting, late night sleeping, Stresshabits, and avoid prolonged sitting and straining during defecation.

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